

Degeneration of the stria vascularis in quiet-aged gerbils: Linking structural, cellular and molecular changes to cochlear function

Sonny Bovee^{a,e}, Carolin Jüchter^a, Georg M. Klump^{a,b,c}, Christine Köppl^{a,b,c},
Sonja J. Pyott^{d,e,f,*}

^a Department of Neuroscience, School of Medicine and Health Science, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Oldenburg 26129, Germany

^b Cluster of Excellence "Hearing4all", Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Oldenburg 26129, Germany

^c Research Centre Neurosensory Science, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Oldenburg 26129, Germany

^d Department of Otorhinolaryngology/Head and Neck Surgery, University Medical Center Groningen, University of Groningen, PO Box 30.001, Groningen 9700 RB, the Netherlands

^e The Research School of Behavioural and Cognitive Neurosciences, University of Groningen, PO Box 30.001, Groningen 9700 RB, the Netherlands

^f Wolfson Sensory, Pain and Regeneration Centre, King's College London, London SE1 1UL, United Kingdom

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Metabolic presbycusis
Age-related hearing loss
Stria vascularis
Ion transport
Gerbil

ABSTRACT

Presbycusis, or age-related hearing loss, is a prevalent condition characterized by progressive auditory decline, significantly impacting quality of life in older adults. While sensorineural damage has been widely studied, degeneration of the stria vascularis (SV) remains underexplored despite its essential role in cochlear ion homeostasis. The SV is organized into three cellular layers—marginal, intermediate, and basal cells—each with distinct functions critical for maintaining the endocochlear potential. Using the quiet-aged Mongolian gerbil—a well-established model of metabolic presbycusis—we systematically mapped the structural and cellular degeneration of the SV and linked these changes to cochlear function. We assessed cochlear function using auditory brainstem response (ABR) measurements and quantified age-related atrophy of the strial cell layers using immunofluorescence, confocal microscopy, and 3D reconstruction. We identified a striking, region-specific pattern of degeneration, with the greatest atrophy occurring in ATP1A1-expressing marginal cells, followed by KCNJ10-expressing intermediate cells, and comparatively little atrophy in CLDN11-expressing basal cells. Notably, atrophy was most pronounced in the cochlear apex and base, regions critical for low- and high-frequency hearing. We further established a significant correlation between the decline in cochlear function and the extent of atrophy of the individual strial cell layers, especially in the cochlear base. By moving beyond traditional cross-sectional assessments of age-related degeneration of the SV, this work provides a more nuanced understanding of how strial pathology contributes to age-related decline in cochlear function and may inform therapeutic interventions targeting strial function to mitigate age-related hearing loss even when sensorineural function is compromised.

1. Introduction

Age-related hearing loss, or presbycusis, affects many aging adults and significantly reduces their quality of life ([World report on hearing, 2021](#)). This decrease in hearing sensitivity is associated with the degeneration of several structures within the peripheral auditory system (for review see ([Heeringa and Köppl, 2019](#); [Keithley, 2020](#); [Eckert et al., 2021](#))) and can be divided into two main categories—sensorineural and

metabolic hearing loss—based on classifications originally proposed by Schuknecht ([Schuknecht, 1955, 1964](#)). The mechanisms underlying presbycusis are not well understood and likely involve interacting mechanisms and mixed sensorineural and strial pathology. Although much attention has focused on sensorineural presbycusis, which involves pathology of the sensory hair cells, spiral ganglion neurons, and the specialized ribbon synapses that form connections between them ([Makary et al., 2011](#); [Sergeyenko et al., 2013](#); [Gleich et al., 2016](#); [Wu](#)

* Corresponding author at: Department of Otorhinolaryngology/Head and Neck Surgery, University Medical Center Groningen, University of Groningen, PO Box 30.001, Groningen 9700 RB, the Netherlands.

E-mail addresses: sonny.bovee@uol.de (S. Bovee), carolin.juechter1@uni-oldenburg.de (C. Jüchter), georg.klump@uni-oldenburg.de (G.M. Klump), christine.koeppel@uol.de (C. Köppl), sonja.pyott@kcl.ac.uk, s.pyott@umcg.nl (S.J. Pyott).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2025.08.004>

et al., 2020; Steenken et al., 2021, Bovee et al., 2024b), metabolic presbycusis, characterized by dysfunction and degeneration of the stria vascularis (SV), the vascularized epithelial tissue located in the lateral wall of the cochlea, is also a key contributor (for review see (Ohlemiller, 2009, Bovee et al., 2024a)). The SV is composed of three cell layers that together maintain the positive endocochlear potential (EP) of around + 80 mV and the high $[K^+]$ concentration in the endolymph that is crucial for sensitive sensory transduction (schematized in Figure 1; for review see (Hibino and Kurachi, 2006; Hibino et al., 2010)). Marginal cells, facing the endolymph, express high levels of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase (and its $\alpha 1$ subunit ATP1A1) and are critical for K^+ secretion and maintenance of the endocochlear potential. Intermediate cells express the inward-rectifier K^+ channel Kir4.1 (KCNJ10), which supports K^+ transport and intrastrial potential generation. Basal cells express the tight junction protein claudin 11 (CLDN11), forming the barrier between the SV and spiral ligament. The molecular architecture and physiological mechanisms of the SV underlying K^+ circulation and generation of the endocochlear potential have been extensively reviewed elsewhere (Hibino and Kurachi, 2006; Hibino et al., 2010). These neurochemical profiles guided our antibody selection and allow cell type-specific volumetric analysis. A recent genome-wide association meta-analysis (Trpchevska et al., 2022) reemphasizes the importance of investigating the contribution and underlying mechanisms of strial pathology in presbycusis to develop effective strategies for treating and preventing presbycusis.

Complementary insights from human histopathological samples and animal models support the link between various functional, structural, and molecular changes in the stria vascularis (SV) that have been associated with presbycusis. Structurally, post-mortem histopathological examinations of the SV in humans consistently show age-related degeneration or atrophy, typically assessed by a reduction in strial cross-sectional area (Pauler et al., 1988; Schuknecht and Gacek, 1993; Kusunoki et al., 2004; Ishiyama et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2020). Similar findings have been reported in multiple mouse strains (Ding et al., 2018; Ohlemiller et al., 2006, 2008), in which strial degeneration is also typically measured as a decrease in strial thickness. Age-related molecular changes in the SV have also been reported in animal models. Most notably, in gerbils, a decline in both Na^+/K^+ -ATPase expression ($\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$ subunits; ATP1A1 and ATP1A2; (Schulte and Schmiedt, 1992)) and function (Gratton et al., 1995) has been reported and also correlated with reduced EP (Schulte and Schmiedt, 1992, Gratton et al., 1997b). Similar age-related changes have been observed in immunoreactivity for the K^+ ion channel Kir4.1 (KCNJ10) in both mice and humans (Liu et al., 2019), and for the $Na^+/K^+/Cl^-$ co-transporter 1 (NKCC1) in

gerbils (Sakaguchi et al., 1998). Although functional measurements of the EP in humans are extremely rare (Kobayashi et al., 1996), age-related decline in the EP has been well documented in Mongolian gerbils (*Meriones unguiculatus*; e.g., (Schmiedt, 1993)), multiple mouse strains (e.g., (Ohlemiller et al., 2006)), and rats (Bielefeld et al., 2008). A mechanistic link between the EP and cochlear function was demonstrated by Schmiedt (1993), who showed that increasing the EP via current injection into the scala media of quiet-aged gerbils—used to avoid confounding effects of noise-induced hearing loss—lowered compound action potential (CAP) thresholds and improved cochlear sensitivity by approximately 20 dB. Conversely, chronic application of furosemide, which lowers EP by inhibiting NKCC1 in the stria vascularis (Edvardsson Rasmussen et al., 2022), reduces CAP amplitudes in young animals, simulating strial dysfunction without aging-related confounds (Schmiedt et al., 2002). While its predominant effect on hearing is attributed to EP reduction, furosemide can modulate outer hair cell (OHC) electromotility in vitro by shifting voltage sensitivity and reducing nonlinear capacitance (Santos-Sacchi et al., 2001). However, these effects occur only at concentrations much higher than the low micromolar levels reached in perilymph and endolymph after intravenous injection (Rybak et al., 1979; Hara et al., 1993). Additionally, in vivo, OHC function shows a two-stage compensatory response to an acutely reduced EP: distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) and OHC region vibrations below the best frequency (BF) recover within approximately one hour, while the BF peak and local cochlear microphonic (LCM) recover more slowly over one to two hours, even as the EP remains subnormal (Wang et al., 2019; Strimbu et al., 2020). These findings suggest not only that furosemide primarily impairs cochlear function through reduction of the EP with minimal direct effects on OHCs at physiologically relevant concentrations but also that OHCs retain some capacity to adapt to an acutely lowered EP.

Although previous studies have identified various age-related changes in the SV associated with metabolic presbycusis, the specific structural alterations, cell-type vulnerabilities, regional variability of degeneration, and their relationship to cochlear function remain largely uncharacterized. Therefore, to better understand how age-related changes in the complex three-dimensional (3D) architecture of the SV relate to decline in cochlear function, we applied new methodology to test whether structural, cellular, and molecular alterations in the entire SV, its distinct regions, and within individual strial cell layers follow specific patterns and correlate with cochlear dysfunction. To this end, we investigated age-related changes in the SV of quiet-aged gerbils, a well-established model of age-related hearing loss (Castaño-González et al., 2024). Gerbils possess sensitive low-frequency hearing similar to

Fig. 1. Schematic of the stria vascularis (SV). Schematic of a cross-section of the cochlea with SV located in the lateral wall (left panel). The SV contains three main cell layers: marginal cells, intermediate cells, and basal cells (right panel). Perivascular macrophage (PVM). Image created with BioRender.com.

humans (Ryan, 1976; Gleich and Strutz, 2012), but, by 36 months of age, they exhibit progressive hearing loss comparable to that in 60–70-year-old humans (Mills et al., 1990). In quiet-aged gerbils, EP decline and reduced cochlear function occur without correlated hair cell loss (Schmiedt et al., 1990; Tarnowski et al., 1991; Steenken et al., 2024), allowing the examination of strial pathology without the confounding effects of noise-induced sensorineural damage. The gerbil was recently used as a model of metabolic presbycusis to identify the metabolic and sensory components of age-related hearing from audiograms in humans (Vaden et al., 2022). In this study, we developed methodology to isolate the SV along the entire cochlear length and assess age-related changes in the cellular and molecular architecture using immunofluorescence and 3D reconstructions. From these reconstructions, we quantified the volumes of immunofluorescently-identified strial cell layers to evaluate age-related atrophy of the strial cell layers across the entire SV as well as in specific cochlear regions (base, middle, and apex). We then correlated these changes with previously assessed cochlear function in the same animals using auditory brainstem response (ABR) measurements. Our results indicate that strial cell layers along the SV and within specific cochlear regions undergo distinct patterns of age-related degeneration and link these patterns to loss of cochlear function. These insights direct strategies to prevent and reduce presbycusis in people.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study design and animals

The study examined age-related changes in the stria vascularis (SV) of quiet-aged Mongolian gerbils (*Meriones unguiculatus*). Primary outcome measures included cochlear function (auditory brainstem response thresholds, amplitudes, and slopes) and SV structural atrophy (measured by immunolabeled volumes of marginal, intermediate, and basal cell layers). To minimize potential confounders, experimental groups were balanced by sex and age, animals were housed in a low-noise environment, and standardized procedures for ABR testing and immunolabeling were used across all samples. Blinding was not employed during the experimental procedures because the primary outcomes assessed (immunolabeled cell layer volumes and ABR thresholds) are quantitative measures that are less susceptible to observer bias. The study protocol was established prior to the start of the study but was not uploaded to a public pre-registration database. A total of 16 gerbils were used: 8 animals (5 females and 3 males) were younger adults aged between 3 and 6 months (control group) while the other 8 (4 females and 4 males) were older animals aged between 36 and 44 months (experimental group). The sample size was consistent with prior studies and justified based on statistical power to detect age-related differences. All animals were born in the animal facility of the University of Oldenburg and housed in a low-noise environment to minimize noise-induced hearing loss (average sound level of 48 and 55 dBA, outside and during working hours, respectively). Animals were included if they were healthy, had no prior noise exposure, and belonged to specified age groups. No exclusions were reported. All protocols and procedures, designed to minimize pain, suffering, and distress while defining and avoiding humane endpoints, were approved by the relevant authorities in Lower Saxony, Germany (permit numbers AZ 33.19–42502–04–16/2208 and AZ 33.19–42502–04–21/3821). No expected or unexpected adverse effects were reported.

2.2. Hearing sensitivity evaluation

Immediately before animals were sacrificed, hearing sensitivity was evaluated by recording click-evoked auditory brainstem responses (ABRs). Anesthesia was administered through an intraperitoneal injection with either a mixture of ketamine (10 % ketamine, 71 mg/kg body weight) and xylazine (2 % xylazine, 3 mg/kg body weight) diluted in

saline (0.9 % NaCl) or a combination of fentanyl (0.005 % fentanyl, 0.03 mg/kg body weight), medetomidine (0.1 % medetomidine, 0.15 mg/kg body weight), and midazolam (0.5 % midazolam, 7.5 mg/kg body weight). Different anesthetics were used depending on the requirements of the regulatory animal license under which the tissues were collected. The anesthesia was maintained with subcutaneous injections of one-third the initial dose. To prevent dehydration, the animals received a 2 mL subcutaneous injection of saline. Throughout the measurements, oxygen was supplied at 0.6 L/min and body temperature was regulated at 37°C using a feedback-controlled homeothermic blanket (Harvard Apparatus). The recordings took place in a sound-attenuating chamber (IAC 401-A, Industrial Acoustics Company). During measurements, the animal's head was fixed using a bite bar. Ear bars with integrated loudspeakers (IE800, Sennheiser) and calibration microphones (ER7-C, Etymotic Research) were placed directly in front of the ear canals. A stainless-steel needle recording electrode was placed under the skin at the vertex of the skull. A second needle electrode was placed under the skin at the midline of the neck and served as a reference. To minimize impedance, saline was applied to the electrodes.

The acoustic system was calibrated in situ at the beginning of each session by measuring the speakers' frequency response using a sine sweep (0.1–22 kHz, logarithmically scaled at 1 octave/s). A finite impulse response filter (512th order) derived from the impulse response obtained with the sine sweep was used to adjust the speakers' output during the measurement, leading to flat output levels (± 3 dB) for frequencies between 0.3 and 19 kHz. ABRs were recorded in response to clicks (0.2–15 kHz, 40 μ s duration), according to previously established methods (Beutelmann et al., 2015), with 10-dB level steps (500 repetitions per level). Stimuli were generated using custom-written software in MATLAB (MathWorks), produced at a 48 kHz sampling rate by an external audio card (Hammerfall DSP Multiface II, RME), and pre-amplified (HB7, Tucker Davis Technologies) before presentation. ABRs were amplified (10,000 times) and bandpass-filtered (0.3–3 kHz) using an amplifier (ISO 80, World Precision Instruments), and digitized using the external audio card (48 kHz sampling rate). ABR thresholds were determined using custom-written software in MATLAB, following an established procedure (Suthakar and Liberman, 2019), and visually cross-checked and adapted if necessary. Additionally, ABR wave I amplitude at 80 dB SPL and ABR wave I slope (using linear regression including data points from 60 to 80 dB) were determined. The ABR (and CAP) threshold reflects the response of the most sensitive auditory-nerve fibers (Kujawa and Liberman, 2009; Furman et al., 2013; Bourien et al., 2014) but is also affected by the endocochlear potential (Sewell, 1984). Both ABR wave I (or CAP) amplitude and ABR wave I slope may represent both synaptopathy (Kujawa and Liberman, 2009; Furman et al., 2013; Sergeyenko et al., 2013; Steenken et al., 2021) as well as the value of the endocochlear potential (Schmiedt et al., 2002; Schmiedt, 2010; Lang et al., 2010).

2.3. Cochlear processing and immunofluorescence

The cochleae were processed based on established protocols (Steenken et al., 2022). Animals were euthanized by administering an overdose of pentobarbital and transcardially perfused with 4 % paraformaldehyde in phosphate buffer (PB). The bullae were extracted and opened in order to make a small hole in the apex and base of the cochleae and were subsequently placed in 4 % paraformaldehyde in PB on a shaker at 8°C for 2 days. The cochleae, which each measure approximately 2.6 mm in diameter and 3.4 mm in height in the mature gerbil (Plassmann et al., 1987), were decalcified in 0.5 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) on a shaker at 8°C for 2 days and then cut in half along the modiolar axis. The tissue was permeabilized for 1 h in 1 % Triton X-100 in PBS and nonspecific binding sites were blocked by incubating in 3 % bovine serum albumin in PBS with 0.2 % Triton X-100 for 1 h.

The following primary antibodies were used: anti-Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase

$\alpha 1$ subunit (ATP1A1) to label marginal cells (mouse monoclonal IgG2a, #a6F concentrate, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, RRID: AB_528092; diluted 1:300) and either anti-K_v4.1 (KCNJ10) to label intermediate cells (rabbit polyclonal IgG, #APC-035, Alomone Labs, RRID: AB_2040120; diluted 1:300) or anti-Claudin 11 (CLDN11) to label basal cells (rabbit polyclonal IgG, #36–4500, ThermoFisher Scientific, RRID: AB_2533259; diluted 1:150). For each animal, the SV from one cochlea was immunolabeled with the anti-ATP1A1 and anti-KCNJ10, while the SV from the other cochlea was immunolabeled with anti-ATP1A1 and anti-CLDN11. Primary antibodies were diluted in blocking solution and the cochleae were incubated for 1 day at 37°C. The following secondary antibodies matching the hosts of the primary antibodies were used: Alexa Fluor 568 goat anti-mouse IgG2a (polyclonal secondary antibody, #A-21134, Thermo Fisher Scientific, RRID: AB_2535773; diluted 1:500) and Alexa Fluor 647 donkey anti-rabbit IgG (polyclonal secondary antibody, #A-31573, Thermo Fisher Scientific, RRID: AB_2536183; diluted 1:500). Secondary antibodies were diluted in blocking solution and the cochleae were incubated for 1 day at 37°C. Finally, the cochleae were micro-dissected under a stereo microscope (Steenken et al., 2022), resulting in typically 9–11 segments of SV, which were mounted on microscope slides in Vectashield Antifade Mounting Medium (Vector Laboratories, H1000). The specificity of the immunofluorescent identification was confirmed by the omission of primary antibodies in control sections.

2.4. Image acquisition

Image stacks of SV segments were obtained using a confocal microscope (Leica TCS SP8 system, Leica Microsystems CMS GmbH). To verify the ability of immunofluorescence labeling to resolve cell types and layers specifically, higher resolution confocal image stacks were first obtained. Subsequently, to expedite scanning of the large number of stacks necessary for quantitative image analysis, lower resolution image stacks were obtained. Specifically, confocal image stacks were acquired in sequential scanning mode with either a 40 × objective (numerical aperture 1.3) at a pixel resolution of 0.45 μm in the x- and y-dimension and steps of 1 μm in the z-dimension or a 10 × objective (numerical aperture 0.3) and pixel resolution of 3 μm in the x- and y-dimension and steps of 5 μm in the z-dimension. Final voxel sizes were 0.45 × 0.45 × 1 μm and 3 × 3 × 5 μm respectively. Fluorescent labels were excited by two different lasers (522 nm optically pumped semiconductor laser and 638 nm laser diode) and emitted photons were counted using a hybrid detector. Crosstalk was excluded by adjusting the detection bandwidth for each channel. The specificity of the secondary antibodies was confirmed by no primary controls. For these controls, images with and without the primary antibodies were acquired using a Nikon epifluorescence microscope system (Nikon ECLIPSE Ni-E with NIS Elements software, Version 4.30) with a 20 × objective (numerical aperture 0.75) and pixel sizes of 0.46 × 0.46 μm and 0.29 × 0.29 μm .

2.5. Image analysis

The length of each segment of SV was measured using ImageJ (Schindelin et al., 2012) and the total length of the SV was calculated for each cochlea. The SV was then subdivided into three tonotopic regions, defined as ‘Apex’, ‘Middle’, and ‘Base’, each representing one-third of the total length, corresponding to low (≈ 0.15 –1.9 kHz), middle (≈ 1.9 –11 kHz), and high (≈ 11 –63 kHz) frequencies respectively (Müller, 1996). If an SV segment contained two tonotopic regions, the segment was cut virtually and the segments assigned to the proper region. To determine the volumes of the different immunolabels, the confocal z-stacks were analyzed using Imaris (version x64 9.7.2, Oxford Instruments) using procedures previously developed for image analysis of the isolated organ of Corti (Reijntjes et al., 2021). Leica LIF files were converted into the native Imaris IMS file format. A mask was created for the region of interest and applied to all channels. Automatic surface

creation was used to construct a 3D model of the labeled structures for each channel, with surface detail smoothing and background subtraction (local contrast) enabled. The threshold was manually adjusted to best reflect the labeled structures. Volume data were exported to XLS files.

2.6. Statistics

A total of 16 Mongolian gerbils (8 young-adult and 8 quiet-aged) were used, providing 31 cochleae for analysis. No outliers were identified, and all collected data were included in analyses. Statistical analysis was carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics version 29 (IBM Corporation). Statistical comparisons between age groups were made using two-tailed independent samples t tests. To assess the difference in volume at the three different tonotopic regions of the SV, a repeated measures mixed model was used, considering also the effect of the individual. Pearson correlation, controlling for age, was used to analyze the correlations between anatomical and physiological measures, treating ears as independent samples. Anatomical and physiological measures were obtained from the same ear. Since immunofluorescent labels were measured independently for each ear, the data are presented as the number of ears. The mixed model ANOVA used accounted for the fact that two ears from the same individual were measured. This approach appropriately considers both related data (two ears from the same individual) and independent data (ears from different individuals). The main effects and two-way interactions are reported. If the assumption of sphericity was not met, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied to adjust the degrees of freedom. Additionally, other factors not measured in this study, such as synapse numbers and EP, have previously been shown to relate to age and influence ABR outcomes. To account for these unknown age-related factors, we used partial correlations between immunolabel volumes and ABR measures of cochlear function using age as the control variable. For all tests a p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

3. Results

3.1. Auditory brainstem response (ABR) measurements confirm age-related decline in cochlear function in quiet-aged gerbils

Before collecting the stria vascularis (SV) from gerbils, their cochlear function was assessed using measurements of click-evoked auditory brainstem responses (ABRs). As expected, ABR wave I thresholds were significantly elevated in quiet-aged gerbils (mean \pm SD; 71.4 \pm 14.7 dB SPL, n = 16) compared to young-adult gerbils (55.7 \pm 8.0 dB SPL, n = 15; Figure 2A). When examining suprathreshold responses, both ABR wave I amplitudes (measured at 80 dB SPL in μV ; Figure 2B) and ABR wave I slopes (measured as the change in ABR wave I amplitudes across 60–80 dB SPL in $\mu\text{V}/\text{dB}$; Figure 2C) were significantly reduced in quiet-aged gerbils (amplitudes: 0.43 \pm 0.52 μV , n = 16; slopes: 0.013 \pm 0.019 $\mu\text{V}/\text{dB}$, n = 16) compared to young-adult gerbils (amplitudes: 0.81 \pm 0.28 μV , n = 15; slopes: 0.028 \pm 0.009 $\mu\text{V}/\text{dB}$, n = 15). These findings validate that the quiet-aged gerbils examined in this study indeed showed age-related decline in cochlear function.

Because the two age groups were deliberately sampled without a uniform or normal distribution of ages in months across the total sample, using age (in months) as a covariate in the ANOVA (rather than age group) would violate basic assumptions of the test and was therefore not performed. Nevertheless, separate regression analyses of age in months versus ABR threshold for the young-adult and old gerbils showed no significant effect of age in the young-adult group, but a highly significant effect in the old group (p < 0.0005). This pattern is consistent with previous observations that young-adult gerbils generally exhibit uniformly low ABR thresholds, whereas older gerbils display a wider range of hearing sensitivity and thresholds (Heeringa, 2024). Including sex as a factor in the analysis revealed neither a main effect nor any significant interactions with location for any of the immunolabels analyzed.

Fig. 2. Cochlear function in young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils. Click-evoked auditory brainstem response (ABR) thresholds (A), wave I amplitudes (B), and wave I slopes (C) are shown for young-adult ($n = 15$) and quiet-aged ($n = 16$) gerbils. Data are represented as boxplots, with boxes indicating the median and interquartile range (IQR), and whiskers extending to 1.5 times the IQR. Outliers, defined as values beyond 1.5 but within 3 times the IQR, are shown as circles. Statistically significant differences between young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils are marked by line brackets, with p-values displayed above the brackets.

3.2. Immunofluorescent labeling of the isolated stria vascularis (SV) identifies the marginal, intermediate and basal cell layers

Immunofluorescent labeling of the isolated SV was used to identify the three cell layers, including the marginal, intermediate and basal cell layers (schematized in Figure 1) based on established patterns of channel and transporter expression. The marginal cell layer, facing the endolymph, was identified using an antibody against the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α 1 subunit (ATP1A1; red, Figure 3A and B; (Hosoya et al., 2022, 2023)). The intermediate cells, forming the middle cell layer, were identified using an antibody against the inwardly rectifying K^+ channel $\text{K}_{\text{ir}}4.1$ (KCNJ10; cyan, Figure 3B; (Trowe et al., 2008, 2011; Korrapati et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2022; Lang et al., 2023)). The basal cell layer, facing the fibrocytes of the spiral ligament, was identified using an antibody against the tight junction protein claudin 11 (CLDN11; magenta, Figure 3A; (Shibata et al., 2016; Korrapati et al., 2019; Taululis et al., 2021; Richard et al., 2023)). For each animal, one SV was double immunolabeled with ATP1A1 and KCNJ10 and the other SV was double immunolabeled with ATP1A1 and CLDN11. When examining the relative localization of immunolabels, there is the expected lack of colocalization of the ATP1A1 and CLDN11 immunolabels, which are restricted to the nonoverlapping marginal and basal cells, respectively (Figure 3A, merge and cross-sections). In contrast, when examining the relative localization of ATP1A1 and KCNJ10 immunolabels, marking the interdigitated marginal and intermediate cells, respectively (Figure 3B, merge, single optical sections, and cross-sections), immunolabels appear in the same planes but nevertheless remain confined to distinct cellular structures. The specificity of the immunofluorescent identification of the particular cell layers of the SV was further confirmed by no primary controls, which showed no immunoreactivity when secondary antibodies were used without primary antibodies (Figure 3C).

3.3. Reconstructions of the isolated and immunolabeled stria vascularis (SV) reveal patterns of atrophy of the marginal, intermediate, and (to a lesser extent) basal cell layers

As a first step to examine age-related changes in the cell layers along the entire length of the stria vascularis (SV), individual images (maximum-intensity z-projections through a stack of confocal micrographs) of immunofluorescently labeled segments (typically 9–11) were assembled to reconstruct the entire SV for each cochlea. Example reconstructions, as well as the approximate tonotopic position, are shown in Figure 4.

When comparing across all samples (mean \pm SD), the average length of the entire SV was 15.29 ± 0.34 mm, with young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils having average lengths of 15.31 ± 0.41 mm and 15.27 ± 0.28 mm, respectively. In young-adult gerbils, absence of ATP1A1

and KCNJ10 labeling was typically seen only at the most apical (low frequency) end of the SV. In quiet-aged gerbils, patchy loss of ATP1A1 and KCNJ10 labeling was observed variably along the length of the SV, with segments from the cochlear apex (low frequency region) and base (high frequency region) being most severely affected. CLDN11 labelling showing comparatively less age-related atrophy.

To quantify age-related changes in strial cell layer volumes, 3D reconstructions of the immunolabeled cell layers from each SV segment were generated from the corresponding confocal micrograph stack. Example 3D reconstructions (from the 5 kHz region) are shown in Figure 5. ATP1A1-expressing marginal cells (red, Figure 5A and B) and KCNJ10-expressing intermediate cells (cyan, Figure 5C and D) are known to show extensive interdigitation, increasing their surface area for interaction and facilitating efficient ion transport (Spicer and Schulte, 2005; Korrapati et al., 2019). The interdigitation between these two cell layers was also revealed in the overlaid 3D reconstructions from double immunolabeled segments (Figure 5E and F). Similar to reconstructions of the entire SV (Figures 4), 3D reconstructions reveal age-related loss of the ATP1A1-expressing marginal cell layer and KCNJ10-expressing intermediate cell layer and little to no age-related changes in the CLDN11-expressing basal cell layer (magenta, Figure 5G and H).

Age-related changes in the strial cell layer volumes from the complete SV as well as the apical, middle and basal tonotopic regions of the SV were quantified from these 3D reconstructions. Compared to young-adult gerbils, in quiet-aged gerbils the volume of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer was significantly reduced by almost half (48 %) in the complete SV as well as in the apical (56 %), middle (36 %) and basal (53 %) tonotopic regions (Figure 6A). A repeated-measures mixed model ANOVA, with ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer volumes at the three tonotopic locations (apex, middle, and base) as within-subject variables and age (young-adult versus quiet-aged) as a between-subject factor, revealed a significant effect of location ($F(2, 58) = 133.898$, $p = 1.8\text{E-}22$). Post-hoc tests confirmed significant volume differences across locations, with the smallest volume at the apex and the largest at the base (apex versus middle: $p = 4.7\text{E-}14$; middle versus base: $p = 8.6\text{E-}04$; apex versus base: $p = 5.5\text{E-}12$). A significant interaction between location and age category ($F(2, 58) = 22.416$, $p = 6.1\text{E-}8$) indicated age-related changes in volume along the tonotopic axis.

Like the marginal cells, the volume of the KCNJ10-labeled intermediate cell layer was significantly reduced (42 %) in the total SV as well as in the apical (46 %), middle (35 %) and basal (46 %) tonotopic regions (Figure 6B). Again, a repeated measures mixed model ANOVA, with KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer volumes at the three tonotopic locations (apex, middle, and base) as within-subject variables and age (young-adult versus quiet-aged) as a between-subject factor,

Fig. 3. Immunofluorescent labeling of the isolated stria vascularis (SV) identifies the marginal, intermediate and basal cell layers. (A) Z-projections from a stack of confocal images of the SV isolated from a quiet-aged gerbil show ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells (red, leftmost panel) and CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cells (magenta, center panel), with minimal overlap in the merged image (rightmost panel). The lack of colocalization between the immunolabels is further highlighted in the digital xz cross-sections displayed below the corresponding panels. (B) Z-projections from a stack of confocal images of the SV isolated from a young-adult gerbil show ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells (red, leftmost panel) and KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cells (cyan, center panel). While the immunolabels appear in the same planes, they remain confined to distinct cellular structures (rightmost panel). The adjacent, non-colocalized immunolabels are better visualized in single optical sections (insets in the corresponding panels) as well as in the digital xz cross-sections displayed below the corresponding panels. (C) Immunolabeling observed with the primary antibody is absent in no primary controls for both secondary antibodies used in this study: Alexa Fluor™ 568 (AF568; leftmost two panels, pixel size is 0.46 \times 0.46 μ m) and Alexa Fluor™ 647 (AF647; rightmost two panels, pixel size is 0.29 \times 0.29 μ m).

revealed a significant effect of location ($F(1.155, 15.020) = 49.297$, $p = 2.3E-06$). Post-hoc tests confirmed significant volume differences across locations, with the smallest volume at the apex and the largest at the base (apex versus middle: $p = 7.5E-11$; middle versus base: $p = 3.9E-02$; apex versus base: $p = 8.3E-06$). A significant interaction between location and age category ($F(1.155, 15.020) = 5.270$, $p = 0.032$) indicated age-related changes in volume along the tonotopic

axis.

Unlike the age-related atrophy of the marginal and intermediate cell layers, the volume of the CLDN11-labeled basal cell layer showed less, but still significant, age-related reduction in the complete SV (12%), and loss was restricted to the basal tonotopic region (20%) with no significant reduction in the apical and middle tonotopic regions (Figure 6C). A repeated measures mixed model ANOVA, with CLDN11-

Fig. 4. Reconstructions of the isolated and immunolabeled stria vascularis (SV) from young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils. (A–B) ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells in the SV from a young-adult (A) and quiet-aged (B) gerbil. (C–D) KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cells in the SV from a young-adult (C) and quiet-aged (D) gerbils. (E–F) CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cells in the SV from a young-adult (E) and quiet-aged (F) gerbil. Reconstructions are shown for the same 5-month-old (young-adult) gerbil and 44-month-old quiet-aged gerbil. Each panel represents a montage of maximum-intensity z-projections through a stack of confocal micrographs. The cochlear tonotopic map and frequency regions corresponding to the apex, middle, and base are shown.

immunolabeled volumes at the three tonotopic locations (apex, middle, and base) as within-subject variables and age (young-adult versus quiet-aged) as a between-subject factor, revealed a significant effect of location ($F(2, 28) = 59.904$, $p = 7.7E-11$). Post-hoc tests confirmed significant volume differences across locations, with the smallest volume at the apex and the largest at the base (apex versus middle: $p = 3.3E-05$; middle versus base: $p = 1.8E-04$; apex vs. base: $p = 4.9E-08$). A significant interaction between location and age category ($F(2, 28) = 3.574$, $p = 0.041$) indicated age-related changes in volume along the tonotopic axis.

3.4. Age-related decline in cochlear function is correlated to the extent of atrophy of the distinct regions and strial cell layers within the stria vascularis (SV)

Finally, we examined the correlation between age-related atrophy of the strial cell layers (Figure 6) and the loss of cochlear function (Figure 2). The total volume of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer showed a significant correlation with ABR wave I threshold (Figure 7A), amplitude (Figure 7D), and slope (Figure 7G). Notably, these correlation coefficients were larger in the basal tonotopic region compared to the total SV (Table 1). The total volume of the KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer was also significantly correlated with ABR wave I threshold (Figure 7B), amplitude (Figure 7E), and slope (Figure 7H), with larger correlation coefficients again observed in the basal tonotopic region compared to the total SV (Table 1). In

contrast, the total volume of the CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cell layer was only significantly correlated with ABR threshold (Figure 7C) but not amplitude (Figure 7F) or slope (Figure 7I). The basal tonotopic region was significantly correlated with both ABR threshold and slope but not amplitude (Table 1).

To exclude the effect of age itself on the correlation between atrophy of the strial cell layers and loss of cochlear function, partial correlations controlling for age were calculated. This approach removes age-related effects, isolating the residual variation in immunolabeled cell layer volumes. After accounting for age, the volume of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer in the base (high-frequency region) remained significantly correlated with ABR wave threshold, amplitude, and slope (Table 1). The total volumes of both the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer and KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer also remained significantly correlated with ABR threshold (Table 1). Finally, only the volume of the KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer in the base (high-frequency region) remained significantly correlated with ABR slope after adjusting for age (Table 1).

In summary, these findings suggest that atrophy of the SV cell layers may either initiate at the cochlear apex and base, progressing toward the middle, or begin uniformly across the cochlea but advance more slowly in the middle region. Moreover, the magnitude of the correlation coefficients suggests that the loss of ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer followed by KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer have the greatest correlation to cochlear function and/or are most closely influenced by the same factors driving hearing loss. In contrast, CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cell layer had only a small effect, which became non-significant after accounting for age. Finally, the basal, high-frequency region of the SV, which has the largest absolute volume, exhibited the largest correlation coefficients with the various ABR metrics of cochlear function, often showing larger correlation coefficients and more significant p-values than the total SV (Table 1).

4. Discussion

Age-related hearing loss (presbycusis) is a multifactorial disorder, with both sensorineural and metabolic contributions. Although previous studies have identified various age-related changes in the SV associated with metabolic presbycusis, the specific contributions of the complex structural alterations, cell-type vulnerabilities, and regional variability of degeneration to age-related decline in cochlear function remain unclear. Our study provides a novel, 3D characterization of SV atrophy in quiet-aged gerbils and its association with cochlear function. Key findings of our study include (1) progressive, cell layer-specific atrophy of the SV, with the greatest loss in ATP1A1-expressing marginal cells, followed by KCNJ10-expressing intermediate cells, and relatively preserved CLDN11-expressing basal cells; (2) regional variation in SV degeneration, with the apex and base exhibiting the most pronounced atrophy; and (3) strong correlations between SV atrophy and loss of cochlear function, with basal atrophy showing the greatest correlations to increased cochlear thresholds. These findings challenge the conventional reliance on cross-sectional area as a measure of SV degeneration, suggesting instead that functional decline may precede gross structural changes in strial thickness.

Our findings align with previous research and also provide new insights. First, the ABR wave I threshold shifts in quiet-aged gerbils (approximately 25 dB at 2 and 10 kHz) are consistent with prior reports using various measures of cochlear function (Mills et al., 1990; Tarnowski et al., 1991; Laumen et al., 2016; Gleich et al., 2016; Heeringa et al., 2020; Steenken et al., 2021). Similar age-related decreases in suprathreshold responses have been previously reported in quiet-aged gerbils and mice (Sergeyenko et al., 2013; Steenken et al., 2021). Second, the age-related changes in ATP1A1, KCNJ10, and CLDN11 expression we observed also align with earlier findings. Loss of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α subunit (ATP1A1 and ATP1A2) immunoreactivity in

Fig. 5. 3D reconstructions of the isolated and immunolabeled stria vascularis (SV) from young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils. (A-B) 3D reconstructions of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells in a segment of the SV from a young-adult (A) and quiet-aged (B) gerbil. (C-D) 3D reconstruction of the KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cells in a segment of the SV from a young-adult (C) and quiet-aged (D) gerbils. (E-F) Overlaid 3D reconstructions of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells (red) and KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cells (cyan) in a segment of the SV from a young-adult (E) and quiet-aged (F) gerbils. (G-H) 3D reconstructions of the CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cells in a segment of the SV from a young-adult (G) and quiet-aged (H) gerbil. 3D reconstructions are shown from the same 5-month-old (young-adult) gerbil and 44-month-old quiet-aged gerbil.

Fig. 6. Strial cell layer volumes in young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils. Volumes for the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer (A), KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer (B), and CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cell layer (C) are shown for young-adult ($n = 15$, blue) and quiet-aged ($n = 16$, red) gerbils for three different tonotopic regions (apex, middle, and base) as well as the entire (total) SV. Data are represented as boxplots, with boxes indicating the median and interquartile range (IQR), and whiskers extending to 1.5 times the IQR. Outliers, defined as values beyond 1.5 but within 3 times the IQR, are shown as circles. Statistically significant differences between young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils are marked by line brackets, with p-values displayed above the brackets.

the SV has been previously reported in quiet-aged gerbils, with the most severe loss occurring in the cochlear apex and base (Schulte and Schmiedt, 1992; Spicer et al., 1997). Functional declines in Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity have also been documented in quiet-aged gerbils (Gratton et al., 1995). In humans, a decrease in ATP1A1 immunoreactivity has been reported in individuals with presbycusis (Stephenson et al., 2021). Age-related decline in $\text{K}_{\text{ir}}4.1$ (KCNJ10) immunoreactivity has also been observed in CBA/CaJ mice as well as in a small sample of human temporal bones (Liu et al., 2019). While age-related decrease in CLDN11 immunoreactivity has not been previously reported, our study found a significant reduction in the SV from the basal, high-frequency regions of the cochlea. Finally, when comparing age-related atrophy in the strial cell layers, we found the greatest loss in volume of the marginal cell layer followed by the intermediate cell layer. This finding

is consistent with previous electron microscopy studies in humans, which reported significant loss of marginal and intermediate cells, particularly in the cochlear apex and base (Takahashi, 1971). We also noted that strial atrophy was greatest in the cochlear base, which showed the largest strial volume in young-adult gerbils. Similarly, in rats the strial width and number of marginal cells in this region was found to be greatest (Lohuis et al., 1990).

Our work is unique in that we could directly correlate age-related decline in cochlear function with the extent of atrophy in specific, identified cell layers of the SV. We found significant correlations between the age-related decline in cochlear function—measured as both ABR wave I thresholds and suprathreshold responses—and the atrophy of ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cells and KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cells and, to a lesser extent, CLDN11-immunolabeled basal

Fig. 7. Correlation between strial cell layer volumes and cochlear function in young-adult and quiet-aged gerbils. Correlation between ABR wave I threshold (A–C), or ABR wave I amplitude (D–F) or ABR wave I slope (G–I) and total volume of the ATP1A1-immunolabeled marginal cell layer (A, D, G), KCNJ10-immunolabeled intermediate cell layer (B, E, H), and CLDN11-immunolabeled basal cell layer (C, F, I). Data are from ears of young-adult (blue; ATP1A1: $n = 15$; KCNJ10: $n = 7$; CLDN11: $n = 8$) and quiet-aged (red, ATP1A1: $n = 16$; KCNJ10: $n = 8$; CLDN11: $n = 8$) gerbils. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R), coefficient of determination (R^2), and p -value are indicated for each panel.

cells. These findings are consistent with previous studies in quiet-aged gerbils, which also demonstrated correlations between age-related decline in endocochlear potential (EP; (Schmiedt, 1996)) and both Na^+/K^+ -ATPase immunoreactivity (Schulte and Schmiedt, 1992) and activity (Gratton et al., 1997b). Thus, structural atrophy and functional

decline of the SV that ultimately result in a lowered EP are all well documented for quiet-aged gerbils. Consequently, the correlation of SV volume metrics and loss of cochlear function observed in the present study implies that a loss of EP was causally involved (although EP was not measured here). The present study re-enforced an important role for

Table 1
Correlations Between Strial Cell Layer (Immunolabel) Volumes and Cochlear Function (ABR Metrics).

Immunolabel volume		Age	ABR wave I threshold		ABR wave I amplitude		ABR wave I/O slope	
		Pearson	Pearson	Partial	Pearson	Partial	Pearson	Partial
ATP1A1	Apex	-0.848	-0.667	-0.339	0.377	-0.025	0.456	0.053
		1.7E-09	4.1E-05	6.7E-02	3.6E-02	9.0E-01	1.0E-02	7.8E-01
	Middle	-0.779	-0.645	-0.329	0.349	-0.013	0.433	0.068
		2.5E-07	8.9E-05	7.6E-02	5.4E-02	9.4E-01	1.5E-02	7.2E-01
Base	-0.899	-0.782	-0.652	0.557	0.374	0.640	0.485	
	6.1E-12	2.1E-07	9.5E-05	1.1E-03	4.2E-02	1.1E-04	6.6E-03	
Total	-0.898	-0.743	-0.539	0.473	0.156	0.555	0.260	
	7.0E-12	1.7E-06	2.1E-03	7.2E-03	4.1E-01	1.2E-03	1.7E-01	
KCNJ10	Apex	-0.900	-0.727	-0.518	0.426	0.079	0.540	0.222
		4.8E-06	2.1E-03	5.8E-02	1.1E-01	7.9E-01	3.8E-02	4.5E-01
	Middle	-0.948	-0.673	-0.381	0.404	-0.043	0.498	0.063
		7.5E-08	6.0E-03	1.8E-01	1.3E-01	8.8E-01	5.9E-02	8.3E-01
Base	-0.840	-0.725	-0.498	0.623	0.520	0.714	0.615	
	8.8E-05	2.2E-03	7.0E-02	1.3E-02	5.7E-02	2.8E-03	1.9E-02	
Total	-0.920	-0.742	-0.584	0.538	0.380	0.640	0.512	
	1.2E-06	1.6E-03	2.8E-02	3.8E-02	1.8E-01	1.0E-02	6.1E-02	
CLDN11	Apex	-0.298	-0.227	-0.052	0.101	-0.056	0.207	0.066
		2.6E-01	4.0E-01	8.5E-01	7.1E-01	8.4E-01	4.4E-01	8.2E-01
	Middle	-0.321	-0.416	-0.291	0.270	0.135	0.324	0.196
		2.3E-01	1.1E-01	2.9E-01	3.1E-01	6.3E-01	2.2E-01	4.8E-01
Base	-0.607	-0.603	-0.356	0.477	0.256	0.534	0.326	
	1.3E-02	1.3E-02	1.9E-01	6.2E-02	3.6E-01	3.3E-02	2.4E-01	
Total	-0.588	-0.536	-0.263	0.398	0.153	0.464	0.234	
	1.7E-02	3.2E-02	3.4E-01	1.3E-01	5.9E-01	7.0E-02	4.0E-01	

Note: Correlation coefficients for Pearson and partial correlations (controlling for age) are shown per immunolabel and per tonotopic region. ATP1A1 (n = 31), KCNJ10 (n = 15), and CLDN11 (n = 16). Significant correlations are shown in bold. Below each correlation coefficient, the corresponding p-value is shown.

degenerative processes in the SV and adds that atrophy of the SV in the cochlear base likely plays a particularly substantive role. Multiple further lines of evidence suggest that the SV in the cochlear base contributes disproportionately to the EP and that a decline in EP affects basal, high-frequency responses disproportionately: 1) the magnitude of the EP increases from the cochlear apex to base (in guinea pigs: (Conlee and Bennett, 1993)); 2) lesions in the lateral wall impair the EP also at locations apical to the damage while leaving the EP at locations basal to the damage unaffected (Wu and Hoshino, 1999), and 3) the impact of EP on the cochlear amplifier is greatest in the cochlear base (Robles and Ruggero, 2001).

However, we also note that our findings do not exclude the possibility that additional factors contribute to age-related, functional decline of the cochlea. Furthermore, while a classic study in quiet-aged gerbils was able to exclude hair-cell loss as a substantial contributor (Tarnowski et al., 1991), more recent work has highlighted the existence of neural presbycusis in quiet-aged gerbils. In fact, loss of ribbon synapses between the inner hair cells and spiral ganglion neurons was shown to correlate with both increased CAP thresholds and decreased CAP suprathreshold amplitudes (Steenken et al., 2021) to a very similar extent as shown here for atrophy of the strial cell layers and ABR metrics. Furthermore, experimental isolation of a decline in EP (by furosemide application in young-adult gerbils (Schmiedt et al., 2002) or a loss of afferent synapses (by ouabain toxicity in young-adult gerbils; (Bourien et al., 2014)) showed that while a reduced EP is the dominant cause of threshold loss, both are able to cause similar functional declines in suprathreshold CAP metrics. Thus, even though the quiet-aged gerbil is classically regarded as an animal model for only metabolic presbycusis (e.g., (Vaden et al., 2022)), it becomes increasingly apparent that its age-related cochlear pathologies are more complex, in particular if functional metrics beyond mere threshold elevations are considered (Heeringa and Köppl, 2019; Steenken et al., 2021; Heeringa et al., 2023, Bovee et al., 2024b; Steenken et al., 2024).

In this study, we quantified age-related atrophy of the strial cell layers by measuring the immunoreactivity of proteins expressed in the various cell types but recognize that more research is needed. Changes in molecular architecture—such as reduced expression of ATP1A1, KCNJ10, and CLDN11—may precede the actual loss of these cells and

atrophy of the SV. In fact, previous examination in mice has shown an age-related decline of approximately 80 % in gene and protein expression of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α 1, β 1, and β 2 subunits (ATP1A1, ATP1B1, and ATP1B2), exceeding the 20 % decrease in SV thickness (Ding et al., 2018). This finding suggests that molecular changes may represent the earliest stage of strial dysfunction, occurring before the morphological atrophy of the SV. Strial degeneration undoubtedly involves other ion channels, such as the Na⁺/K⁺/Cl⁻ co-transporter 1 (NKCC1; (Sakaguchi et al., 1998)), as well as additional mechanisms (reviewed in (Bovee et al., 2024a)). These mechanisms include vascular atrophy, observed in the SV of both gerbils (Gratton and Schulte, 1995; Gratton et al., 1996, 1997a; Thomopoulos et al., 1997) and humans (Kurata et al., 2016), as well as aberrant macrophage activity and “inflammaging,” observed in the SV of mice and humans (Lang et al., 2023). Ultimately, to gain deeper insights into the complex processes contributing to presbycusis, which cannot be fully modeled by any single animal model, future studies should aim to combine functional and structural measures, examine multiple time points, and investigate various animal models.

Translating our findings in gerbils—particularly the relative contributions of sensorineural and metabolic presbycusis to hearing loss in humans—is challenging due to differences in intrinsic (genetic) and extrinsic (environmental) factors, especially noise exposure. Notably, recent histopathologic analyses and statistical modeling of human cochlear samples, many from individuals with recent audiograms, concluded that while significant strial degeneration was observed throughout the cochlea of most older individuals, hair cell loss was the best predictor of hearing loss (Wu et al., 2020). These findings suggest that, unlike in gerbils, strial presbycusis may not be a major contributor to presbycusis in humans. These findings may reflect true species-specific differences in patterns of cochlear aging. However, as recently reviewed (Eckert et al., 2021, Bovee et al., 2024a), there is a complex relationship between hair cells and the strial battery, with loss of hair cells reducing the metabolic load on the stria vascularis. This link between hair cell and strial pathologies was also noted by Vaden and coauthors (Vaden et al., 2022), who suggested that noise-related loss of OHCs may explain the poor correlation between strial atrophy (assessed as cross-sectional area) and hearing thresholds observed by Wu and coauthors (Wu et al., 2020). Our findings from the present work

highlight an additional possible caveat: strial atrophy, particularly when measured by cross-sectional area, may not accurately reflect remaining strial function, as functional decline can precede detectable structural loss. Thus, the quiet-aged gerbil, in which OHC loss is minimized, may bring out the effect of strial atrophy more clearly. Finally, even if strial pathology is secondary to sensorineural pathology in human presbycusis, the common co-occurrence of strial atrophy with sensorineural loss indicates that addressing strial degeneration will also be important in efforts to prevent or restore age-related hearing loss.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we developed novel methodologies to investigate the complex cellular and 3D architecture of the gerbil SV. Combining these approaches with functional measures, we identified significant correlations between age-related decline in cochlear function and the extent of atrophy in specific cell layers of the SV. The significant correlation between age-related strial degeneration and deficits in cochlear function underscores the importance of targeting strial dysfunction in therapeutic strategies to combat presbycusis. While current interventions for presbycusis primarily focus on hair cell and synapse preservation, our findings suggest that preserving or restoring strial function may mitigate hearing loss even in cases where sensorineural damage is present and, therefore, complement efforts aimed at preventing or restoring sensorineural hearing loss, including limiting noise exposure. Our work suggests specific avenues for intervention, including enhancing ion transporter function to stabilize and/or restore the endocochlear potential as well as developing pharmacological or genetic strategies to preserve strial integrity. Powered by the findings and approaches developed in this work, future work should aim to expand molecular analyses using transcriptomic and proteomic approaches to identify additional molecular contributors to age-related decline in strial function, integrate potential interactions between strial and sensorineural pathology to better distinguish their contributions to age-related loss of cochlear function, and finally compare age-related decline in strial function across different animal models to determine species-specific differences and improve translation to human presbycusis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sonja J. Pyott: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christine Köppl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Carolin Jüchter:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Georg M. Klump:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sonny Bovee:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Funding sources

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy –EXC 2177/1 - Project ID 390895286) and the Dutch Heinsius Houbolt Foundation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in

order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no known conflict of interests, including financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank Dr. Sandra Tolnai for help with ABR measurements. We also acknowledge the Fluorescence Microscopy Service Unit, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, for the use of their imaging facilities. Additionally, part of the work has been performed at the UMCG Imaging and Microscopy Center (UMIC), which is sponsored by the UMCG.

References

- Beutelmann, R., Laumen, G., Tollin, D., Klump, G.M., 2015. Amplitude and phase equalization of stimuli for click evoked auditory brainstem responses. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 137, EL71–EL77. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4903921>.
- Bielefeld, E.C., Coling, D., Chen, G.-D., Li, M., Tanaka, C., Hu, B.-H., et al., 2008. Age-related hearing loss in the fischer 344/NHsd rat substrain. *Hear Res* 241, 26–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2008.04.006>.
- Bourien, J., Tang, Y., Batrel, C., Huet, A., Lenoir, M., Ladrech, S., et al., 2014. Contribution of auditory nerve fibers to compound action potential of the auditory nerve. *J. Neurophysiol.* 112, 1025–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00738.2013>.
- Bovee, S., Klump, G.M., Pyott, S.J., Sielaff, C., Köppl, C., 2024b. Cochlear ribbon synapses in aged gerbils. *Int J. Mol. Sci.* 25, 2738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25052738>.
- Bovee, S., Klump, G.M., Köppl, C., Pyott, S.J., 2024a. The stria vascularis: renewed attention on a key player in age-related hearing loss. *Int J. Mol. Sci.* 25, 5391. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25105391>.
- Castano-González, K., Köppl, C., Pyott, S.J., 2024. The crucial role of diverse animal models to investigate cochlear aging and hearing loss. *Hear Res* 445, 108989. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2024.108989>.
- Conlee, J.W., Bennett, M.L., 1993. Turn-specific differences in the endocochlear potential between albino and pigmented Guinea pigs. *Hear Res* 65, 141–150. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(93\)90209-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(93)90209-J).
- Ding, B., Walton, J.P., Zhu, X., Frisina, R.D., 2018. Age-related changes in na, K-ATPase expression, subunit isoform selection and assembly in the stria vascularis lateral wall of mouse cochlea. *Hear Res* 367, 59–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2018.07.006>.
- Eckert, M.A., Harris, K.C., Lang, H., Lewis, M.A., Schmiedt, R.A., Schulte, B.A., et al., 2021. Translational and interdisciplinary insights into presbycusis: a multidimensional disease. *Hear Res* 402, 108109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2020.108109>.
- Edvardsson Rasmussen, J., Lundström, P., Eriksson, P.O., Rask-Andersen, H., Liu, W., Laurell, G., 2022. The acute effects of furosemide on Na-K-Cl cotransporter-1, fetuin-A and pigment epithelium-derived factor in the Guinea pig cochlea. *Front Mol. Neurosci.* 15, 842132. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2022.842132>.
- Furman, A.C., Kujawa, S.G., Liberman, M.C., 2013. Noise-induced cochlear neuropathy is selective for fibers with low spontaneous rates. *J. Neurophysiol.* 110, 577–586. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00164.2013>.
- Gleich, O., Strutz, J., 2012. The Mongolian gerbil as a model for the analysis of peripheral and central age-dependent hearing loss. In: Naz, S. (Ed.), *Hearing Loss. InTech*, pp. 67–92.
- Gleich, O., Semmler, P., Strutz, J., 2016. Behavioral auditory thresholds and loss of ribbon synapses at inner hair cells in aged gerbils. *Exp. Gerontol.* 84, 61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exger.2016.08.011>.
- Gratton, M.A., Schulte, B.A., 1995. Alterations in microvasculature are associated with atrophy of the stria vascularis in quiet-aged gerbils. *Hear Res* 82, 44–52. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(94\)00161-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(94)00161-L).
- Gratton, M.A., Smyth, B.J., Schulte, B.A., Vincent, D.A., 1995. Na,K-ATPase activity decreases in the cochlear lateral wall of quiet-aged gerbils. *Hear Res* 83, 43–50. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(94\)00188-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(94)00188-V).
- Gratton, M.A., Schmiedt, R.A., Schulte, B.A., 1996. Age-related decreases in endocochlear potential are associated with vascular abnormalities in the stria vascularis. *Hear Res* 102, 181–190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(96\)90017-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(96)90017-9).
- Gratton, M.A., Schulte, B.A., Smyth, N.M., 1997a. Quantification of the stria vascularis and strial capillary areas in quiet-reared young and aged gerbils. *Hear Res* 114, 1–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(97\)00025-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(97)00025-7).
- Gratton, M.A., Smyth, B.J., Lam, C.F., Boettcher, F.A., Schmiedt, R.A., 1997b. Decline in the endocochlear potential corresponds to decreased Na,K-ATPase activity in the lateral wall of quiet-aged gerbils. *Hear Res* 108, 9–16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(97\)00034-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(97)00034-8).

- Hara, A., Machiki, K., Senarita, M., Komeno, M., Kusakari, J., 1993. Pharmacokinetics of furosemide in endolymph. *Auris Nasus Larynx* 20, 247–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0385-8146\(12\)80116-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0385-8146(12)80116-7).
- Heeringa, A.N., 2024. Single-unit data for sensory neuroscience: responses from the auditory nerve of young-adult and aging gerbils. *Sci. Data* 11, 411. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03259-3>.
- Heeringa, A.N., Köppl, C., 2019. The aging cochlea: towards unraveling the functional contributions of stria dysfunction and synaptopathy. *Hear Res* 376, 111–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2019.02.015>.
- Heeringa, A.N., Zhang, L., Ashida, G., Beutelmann, R., Steenken, F., Köppl, C., 2020. Temporal coding of single auditory nerve fibers is not degraded in aging gerbils. *J. Neurosci.* 40, 343–354. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2784-18.2019>.
- Heeringa, A.N., Teske, F., Ashida, G., Köppl, C., 2023. Cochlear aging disrupts the correlation between spontaneous rate and sound-level coding in auditory nerve fibers. *J. Neurophysiol.* 130, 736–750. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00090.2023>.
- Hibino, H., Kurachi, Y., 2006. Molecular and physiological bases of the K^+ circulation in the mammalian inner ear. *Physiology* 21, 336–345. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physiol.00023.2006>.
- Hibino, H., Nin, F., Tsuzuki, C., Kurachi, Y., 2010. How is the highly positive endocochlear potential formed? The specific architecture of the stria vascularis and the roles of the ion-transport apparatus. *Pflug. Arch. Eur. J. Physiol.* 459, 521–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00424-009-0754-z>.
- Hosoya, M., Kitama, T., Iwabu, K., Nishiyama, T., Oishi, N., Okano, H., et al., 2022. Development of the stria vascularis in the common marmoset, a primate model. *Sci. Rep.* 12, 19811. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-24380-6>.
- Hosoya, M., Kitama, T., Shimanuki, M.N., Nishiyama, T., Oishi, N., Okano, H., et al., 2023. Distribution of macrophages in the developing cochlea of the common marmoset, a primate model animal. *Front Immunol.* 14, 1229414. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1229414>.
- Ishiyama, G., Tokita, J., Lopez, I., Tang, Y., Ishiyama, A., 2007. Unbiased stereological estimation of the spiral ligament and stria vascularis volumes in aging and Ménière's disease using archival human temporal bones. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 8, 8–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10162-006-0057-4>.
- Keithley, E.M., 2020. Pathology and mechanisms of cochlear aging. *J. Neurosci. Res* 98, 1674–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnr.24439>.
- Kobayashi, T., Aslan, A., Chiba, T., Takasaka, T., Sanna, M., 1996. Measurement of endocochlear DC potentials in ears with acoustic neuromas: a preliminary report. *Acta Otolaryngol. (Stock.)* 116, 791–795. <https://doi.org/10.3109/00016489609137927>.
- Korrapati, S., Taukulis, I., Olszewski, R., Pyle, M., Gu, S., Singh, R., et al., 2019. Single cell and single nucleus RNA-seq reveal cellular heterogeneity and homeostatic regulatory networks in adult mouse stria vascularis. *Front Mol. Neurosci.* 12, 316. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2019.00316>.
- Kujawa, S.G., Liberman, M.C., 2009. Adding insult to injury: cochlear nerve degeneration after “temporary” noise-induced hearing loss. *J. Neurosci.* 29, 14077–14085. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2845-09.2009>.
- Kurata, N., Schachern, P.A., Paparella, M.M., Cureoglu, S., 2016. Histopathologic evaluation of vascular findings in the cochlea in patients with presbycusis. *JAMA Otolaryngol. Neck Surg.* 142, 173. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoto.2015.3163>.
- Kusunoki, T., Cureoglu, S., Schachern, P.A., Baba, K., Kariya, S., Paparella, M.M., 2004. Age-related histopathologic changes in the human cochlea: a temporal bone study. *Otolaryngol. Neck Surg.* 131, 897–903. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.otohns.2004.05.022>.
- Lang, H., Jyothi, V., Smythe, N.M., Dubno, J.R., Schulte, B.A., Schmiedt, R.A., 2010. Chronic reduction of endocochlear potential reduces auditory nerve activity: further confirmation of an animal model of metabolic presbycusis. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 11, 419–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10162-010-0214-7>.
- Lang, H., Noble, K.V., Barth, J.L., Rumschlag, J.A., Jenkins, T.R., Storm, S.L., et al., 2023. The stria vascularis in mice and humans is an early site of age-related cochlear degeneration, macrophage dysfunction, and inflammation. *J. Neurosci.* 43, 5057–5075. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2234-22.2023>.
- Laumen, G., Tollin, D.J., Beutelmann, R., Klump, G.M., 2016. Aging effects on the binaural interaction component of the auditory brainstem response in the Mongolian gerbil: effects of interaural time and level differences. *Hear Res* 337, 46–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2016.04.009>.
- Liu, T., Li, G., Noble, K.V., Li, Y., Barth, J.L., Schulte, B.A., et al., 2019. Age-dependent alterations of Kir4.1 expression in neural crest-derived cells of the mouse and human cochlea. *Neurobiol. Aging* 80, 210–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2019.04.009>.
- Lohuis, P.J.F.M., Patterson, K., Rarey, K.E., 1990. Quantitative assessment of the rat stria vascularis. *Hear Res* 47, 95–102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(90\)90169-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(90)90169-P).
- Makary, C.A., Shin, J., Kujawa, S.G., Liberman, M.C., Merchant, S.N., 2011. Age-related primary cochlear neuronal degeneration in human temporal bones. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 12, 711–717. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10162-011-0283-2>.
- Mills, J.H., Schmiedt, R.A., Kulish, L.F., 1990. Age-related changes in auditory potentials of Mongolian gerbil. *Hear Res* 46, 201–210. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(90\)90002-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(90)90002-7).
- Müller, M., 1996. The cochlear place-frequency map of the adult and developing Mongolian gerbil. *Hear Res* 94, 148–156. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(95\)00230-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(95)00230-8).
- Ohlemiller, K.K., 2009. Mechanisms and genes in human stria presbycusis from animal models. *Brain Res* 1277, 70–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2009.02.079>.
- Ohlemiller, K.K., Lett, J.M., Gagnon, P.M., 2006. Cellular correlates of age-related endocochlear potential reduction in a mouse model. *Hear Res* 220, 10–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2006.06.012>.
- Ohlemiller, K.K., Rice, M.E.R., Gagnon, P.M., 2008. Strial microvascular pathology and age-associated endocochlear potential decline in NOD congenic mice. *Hear Res* 244, 85–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2008.08.001>.
- Pauler, M., Schuknecht, H.F., White, J.A., 1988. Atrophy of the stria vascularis as a cause of sensorineural hearing loss. *Laryngoscope* 98, 754–759. <https://doi.org/10.1288/00005537-198807000-00014>.
- Plassmann, W., Peetz, W., Schmidt, M., 1987. The cochlea in gerbilline rodents. *Brain Behav. Evol.* 30, 82–102. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000118639>.
- Reijntjes, D.O.J., Breitzler, J.L., Persic, D., Pyott, S.J., 2021. Preparation of the intact rodent organ of corti for RNAscope and immunolabeling, confocal microscopy, and quantitative analysis. *STAR Protoc.* 2, 100544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xpro.2021.100544>.
- Richard, E.M., Brun, E., Korchagina, J., Crouzier, L., Affortit, C., Alves, S., et al., 2023. Wfs1E864K knock-in mice illuminate the fundamental role of Wfs1 in endocochlear potential production. *Cell Death Dis.* 14, 387. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41419-023-05912-y>.
- Robles, L., Ruggero, M.A., 2001. Mechanics of the mammalian cochlea. *Physiol. Rev.* 81, 1305–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.2001.81.3.1305>.
- Ryan, A., 1976. Hearing sensitivity of the Mongolian gerbil, *Meriones unguiculatus*. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 59, 1222–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.380961>.
- Rybak, L.P., Green, T.P., Juhn, S.K., Morizono, T., Mirkin, B.L., 1979. Elimination kinetics of furosemide in perilymph and serum of the chinchilla: *neuropharmacologic correlates*. *Acta Otolaryngol. (Stock.)* 88, 382–387. <https://doi.org/10.3109/00016487909137182>.
- Sakaguchi, N., Crouch, J.J., Lytle, C., Schulte, B.A., 1998. Na-K-Cl cotransporter expression in the developing and senescent gerbil cochlea. *Hear Res* 118, 114–122. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(98\)00022-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(98)00022-7).
- Santos-Sacchi, J., Wu, M., Kakehata, S., 2001. Furosemide alters nonlinear capacitance in isolated outer hair cells. *Hear Res* 159, 69–73. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(01\)00321-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(01)00321-5).
- Schindelin, J., Arganda-Carreras, I., Frise, E., Kaynig, V., Longair, M., Pietzsch, T., et al., 2012. Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis. *Nat. Methods* 9, 676–682. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2019>.
- Schmiedt, R.A., 1993. Cochlear potentials in quiet-aged gerbils: does the aging cochlea need a jump start? In: Verrillo, R.T., Zwislocki, J.J. (Eds.), *Sensory Research: Multimodal Perspectives*. L. Erlbaum Associates, Hillsdale, N.J., pp. 91–103.
- Schmiedt, R.A., 1996. Effects of aging on potassium homeostasis and the endocochlear potential in the gerbil cochlea. *Hear Res* 102, 125–132. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(96\)00154-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(96)00154-2).
- Schmiedt, R.A., 2010. The physiology of cochlear presbycusis. In: Gordon-Salant, S., Frisina, R.D., Popper, A.N., Fay, R.R. (Eds.), *The Aging Auditory System*. Springer New York, New York, NY, pp. 9–38.
- Schmiedt, R.A., Mills, J.H., Adams, J.C., 1990. Tuning and suppression in auditory nerve fibers of aged gerbils raised in quiet or noise. *Hear Res* 45, 221–236. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(90\)90122-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(90)90122-6).
- Schmiedt, R.A., Lang, H., Okamura, H., Schulte, B.A., 2002. Effects of furosemide applied chronically to the round window: a model of metabolic presbycusis. *J. Neurosci.* 22, 9643–9650. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.22-21-09643.2002>.
- Schuknecht, H.F., 1955. Presbycusis. *Laryngoscope* 65, 402–419. <https://doi.org/10.1288/00005537-195506000-00002>.
- Schuknecht, H.F., 1964. Further observations on the pathology of presbycusis. *Arch. Otolaryngol.* 80, 369–382. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archotol.1964.00750040381003>.
- Schuknecht, H.F., Gacek, M.R., 1993. Cochlear pathology in presbycusis. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.* 102, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000348949310208101>.
- Schulte, B.A., Schmiedt, R.A., 1992. Lateral wall na, K-ATPase and endocochlear potentials decline with age in quiet-reared gerbils. *Hear Res* 61, 35–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(92\)90034-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(92)90034-K).
- Sergeyenko, Y., Lall, K., Liberman, M.C., Kujawa, S.G., 2013. Age-related cochlear synaptopathy: an early-onset contributor to auditory functional decline. *J. Neurosci.* 33, 13686–13694. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1783-13.2013>.
- Sewell, W.F., 1984. The relation between the endocochlear potential and spontaneous activity in auditory nerve fibres of the cat. *J. Physiol.* 347, 685–696. <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1984.sp015090>.
- Shibata, S., Miwa, T., Wu, H.-H., Levitt, P., Ohyama, T., 2016. Hepatocyte growth factor-c-MET signaling mediates the development of nonsensory structures of the mammalian cochlea and hearing. *J. Neurosci.* 36, 8200–8209. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4410-15.2016>.
- Spicer, S.S., Schulte, B.A., 2005. Pathologic changes of presbycusis begin in secondary processes and spread to primary processes of stria marginal cells. *Hear Res* 205, 225–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2005.03.022>.
- Spicer, S.S., Gratton, M.A., Schulte, B.A., 1997. Expression patterns of ion transport enzymes in spiral ligament fibrocytes change in relation to stria atrophy in the aged gerbil cochlea. *Hear Res* 111, 93–102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(97\)00097-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(97)00097-X).
- Steenken, F., Heeringa, A.N., Beutelmann, R., Zhang, L., Bovee, S., Klump, G.M., et al., 2021. Age-related decline in cochlear ribbon synapses and its relation to different metrics of auditory-nerve activity. *Neurobiol. Aging* 108, 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2021.08.019>.
- Steenken, F., Bovee, S., Köppl, C., 2022. Immunolabeling and counting ribbon synapses in young adult and aged gerbil cochlea. *J. Vis. Exp.* 63874. <https://doi.org/10.3791/63874>.
- Steenken, F., Pektaş, A., Köppl, C., 2024. Age-related changes in olivocochlear efferent innervation in gerbils. *Front Synaptic Neurosci.* 16, 1422330. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsyn.2024.1422330>.

- Stephenson, R., Mangasarian, A., Ishiyama, G., Hosokawa, K., Hosokawa, S., Ishiyama, A., et al., 2021. Immunohistochemical location of na⁺, K⁺-ATPase α 1 subunit in the human inner ear. *Hear Res* 400, 108113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2020.108113>.
- Strimbu, C.E., Wang, Y., Olson, E.S., 2020. Manipulation of the endocochlear potential reveals two distinct types of cochlear nonlinearity. *Biophys. J.* 119, 2087–2101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpj.2020.10.005>.
- Sun, G., Zheng, Y., Fu, X., Zhang, W., Ren, J., Ma, S., et al., 2022. Single-cell transcriptomic Atlas of mouse cochlear aging. *Protein Cell*, pwac058. <https://doi.org/10.1093/procel/pwac058>.
- Suthakar, K., Liberman, M.C., 2019. A simple algorithm for objective threshold determination of auditory brainstem responses. *Hear Res* 381, 107782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2019.107782>.
- Takahashi, T., 1971. The ultrastructure of the pathologic stria vascularis and spiral prominence in man. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.* 80, 721–735. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000348947108000515>.
- Tarnowski, B.I., Schmiedt, R.A., Hellstrom, L.I., Lee, F.S., Adams, J.C., 1991. Age-related changes in cochleas of Mongolian gerbils. *Hear Res* 54, 123–134. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955\(91\)90142-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5955(91)90142-V).
- Taukulis, I.A., Olszewski, R.T., Korrapati, S., Fernandez, K.A., Boger, E.T., Fitzgerald, T. S., et al., 2021. Single-cell RNA-seq of cisplatin-treated adult stria vascularis identifies cell type-specific regulatory networks and novel therapeutic gene targets. *Front Mol. Neurosci.* 14, 718241. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2021.718241>.
- Thomopoulos, G.N., Spicer, S.S., Gratton, M.A., Schulte, B.A., 1997. Age-related thickening of basement membrane in stria vascularis capillaries. *Hear Res* 111, 31–41. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955\(97\)00080-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5955(97)00080-4).
- Trowe, M.-O., Maier, H., Schweizer, M., Kispert, A., 2008. Deafness in mice lacking the T-box transcription factor Tbx18 in otic fibrocytes. *Development* 135, 1725–1734. <https://doi.org/10.1242/dev.014043>.
- Trowe, M.-O., Maier, H., Petry, M., Schweizer, M., Schuster-Gossler, K., Kispert, A., 2011. Impaired stria vascularis integrity upon loss of E-cadherin in basal cells. *Dev. Biol.* 359, 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ydbio.2011.08.030>.
- Trpchevska, N., Freidin, M.B., Broer, L., Oosterloo, B.C., Yao, S., Zhou, Y., et al., 2022. Genome-wide association meta-analysis identifies 48 risk variants and highlights the role of the stria vascularis in hearing loss. *Am. J. Hum. Genet* 109, 1077–1091. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajhg.2022.04.010>.
- Vaden, K.I., Eckert, M.A., Matthews, L.J., Schmiedt, R.A., Dubno, J.R., 2022. Metabolic and sensory components of age-related hearing loss. *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* 23, 253–272. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10162-021-00826-y>.
- Wang, Y., Fallah, E., Olson, E.S., 2019. Adaptation of cochlear amplification to low endocochlear potential. *Biophys. J.* 116, 1769–1786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpj.2019.03.020>.
- World report on hearing. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021.
- Wu, P.-Z., O'Malley, J.T., de Gruttola, V., Liberman, M.C., 2020. Age-related hearing loss is dominated by damage to inner ear sensory cells, not the cellular battery that powers them. *J. Neurosci.* 40, 6357–6366. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0937-20.2020>.
- Wu, R., Hoshino, T., 1999. Changes in off-lesion endocochlear potential following localized lesion in the lateral wall. *Acta Otolaryngol. (Stock.)* 119, 550–554. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00016489950180775>.